

Processing of PEEK/PEI Blends for High Performance Composites in Aerospace

Michele Iannone^{1,a)}

¹*Leonardo Aircraft*

^{a)}*Corresponding author: michele.iannone@leonardocompany.com*

Abstract. A new approach has been considered for aeronautical composite structures with thermoplastic matrix. The new concept is based on the addition of amorphous PEI films to a semicrystalline thermoplastic PEEK/Carbon Fiber prepreg. The performed chemical-physical analysis demonstrate the good blending between the two resins. The new approach, being presently developed in a project funded by EU, could allow to perform structural parts with affordable costs through the utilization of automated lay-up (ATL and/or AFP) techniques, with a strong cost saving due to the elimination of the autoclave cycle.

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of composite materials for aeronautical structures reached recently a very high level, in agreement with the best hopes of the composite community. The Boeing 787 and the Airbus A350 are two recent wide-body airliners with all the major primary structures (fuselage, wings, empennages) in composite, with a percent weight of composite of about 50%. The typical composition of the composite materials utilized to perform these structures is based on a thermosetting epoxy matrix reinforced with carbon fiber.

A consideration that for some aspects could be surprising is that, beside a growing utilization of thermoplastic matrix composites for interior and secondary structure applications, there is still a very limited use of thermoplastic for primary structures. There are several potential advantages offered by thermoplastics, which don't need refrigerated transport and storage, don't have expiring time, are generally tough, thermally stable (with good high temperature and fire behavior), can be welded and recycled. Despite of that today the composite utilization for aeronautical primary structures is mainly based on thermosetting resins. Beside some reasons based on historical considerations, being the thermoset matrix composites more known and due to the situation of the existing production plants in favor of thermosets, a very important issue is cost. In fact the thermoplastics suitable for primary structural applications are generally semicrystalline, like PEEK, PEKK and in limited amount PPS, for the severe structural and environmental (temperature, solvents and humidity) strength requirements. Presently the raw material costs of thermoplastic matrix composites made with the mentioned resins is higher than the one of thermosets. A key issue is the comparison of the structure cost fabrication with thermosets matrix prepreps vs the one with thermoplastic matrix prepreps.

The process technology generally used to fabricate composite parts with thermosetting prepreps is based on lay-up plus autoclave. A stacking of prepreg layers is created by hand or, more recently, by automated lay-up technique (automated tape lay-up ATL for flat or low curvature shapes or Automated Fiber Placement AFP for severe or double curvature shapes, using narrow tapes called slits). Then the uncured lay-up is put in a vacuum bag and processed at high temperature and pressure (about 180 °C and 6 atm. for 90-120 min) in autoclave.

For thermoplastics the technological challenge is different; in fact the material is already polymerized and in order to be consolidated in laminates it needs to be heated at a temperature above T_g (or above T_m for semi-crystalline thermoplastics), consolidated under pressure and cooled. The holding time at high temperature depends only from time needed for shaping and consolidating and is generally much shorter than for thermosets, where a long time for polymerization completion is required. Consequently for thermoplastics techniques like thermoforming, using preheating and cold presses, are much diffused for several applications, e.g. for automotive. For aeronautical thermoforming is also used, but the maximum size (depending on press size) and the feasible shapes (the technique is not the best for double curvature and/or small curvature radius parts) give some limitations, mainly for large primary applications.

A very important specific issue is given by ATL and AFP of thermoplastic matrix prepreg. These technique have been previously mentioned for thermoset matrix prepregs, where they substitute hand lay-up, with cost saving and quality improvement, but yet requires bagging and autoclaving to obtain final parts. For thermosets lay-up (both by hand and automated) is possible for the uncured prepreg tackiness. For thermoplastic lay-up becomes possible only above T_g for amorphous resins and above T_m for semi-crystalline resins, and consequently ATL and AFP require also the utilization of a heating source (e.g. hot gas or laser); then ATL and AFP are technologically more difficult for thermoplastics, but, if successful, they are potentially much cheaper because the final product can be obtained during lay-up and a following phase of bagging plus autoclave isn't required. The major difficulties are given by the already mentioned very high temperature required (e.g. for PEEK above 350 °C) and, mainly for semi-crystalline thermoplastics, by the need of a cooling with a controlled rate, because cooling rate can affect the crystallinity content of the final product and must be included in a processing window. (Ref. 1)

A new approach has been proposed to simplify both the major difficulties (high temperature and controlled cooling rate) based on the utilization of a semi-crystalline matrix (PEEK). It is based on the utilization of a carbon fiber reinforced prepreg material with the addition of two external layers of amorphous thermoplastic (PEI) films (Ref.2). The hybrid prepreg is fabricated with a process under pressure (e.g. with a press) based on heating both prepreg and amorphous layers at a temperature above T_m and then cooling with a controlled cooling rate. The obtained hybrid prepreg layer, shown in a sketch (fig. 1), can be utilized in producing lay-ups at a temperature above the T_g of the amorphous layer.

FIGURE 1. Sketch of a hybrid semicrystalline-amorphous thermoplastic matrix prepreg

Furthermore the required control on cooling rate is less severe, in fact the crystals aren't involved, due to the maximum temperature below T_m . That simplify the ATL and AFP processes or allow a process in autoclave at a temperature just slightly higher than for thermosets.

The development of AFP composite structures based on the hybrid semicrystalline-amorphous thermoplastic matrix prepreg concept is presently being investigated in the EC funded research project, "New Hybrid Thermoplastic Composite Aerostructures manufactured by Out of Autoclave Continuous Automated Technologies" (NHYTE).

The hybrid prepreg is basically made by PEEK resin with carbon fiber in the central zone, and by PEI in the external one. In the zone of transition from PEEK to PEI, with a progressively changing percentage from 100% of PEEK to 100% of PEI, there are blends with characteristics investigated in a previous work (Ref. 3).

A study on the behavior of blends PEEK-PEI carried in a previous work confirmed the complete compatibility of PEEK with PEI. When analyzed by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), the blends with different compositions showed a crystalline phase with constant characteristics (T_{onset} , T_{peak} , etc.) at all the compositions, except for the crystalline amount which is proportional to the PEEK content (fig. 2). The amorphous phase showed a complete blending, with a unique T_g linearly changing with the composition (fig.3).

FIGURE 2. Melting Peak Area of PEEK/PEI blends with different compositions

FIGURE 3. T_g of PEEK/PEI blends with different compositions

CONCLUSIONS

A new concept of hybrid thermoplastic matrix prepreg, based on the addition of amorphous thermoplastic (PEI) layers to a semi-crystalline matrix (PEEK) carbon fiber reinforced prepreg is under investigation. Potential cost saving due to the possibility of fabrication by automated lay-up without autoclave cycle could allow a larger utilization for thermoplastic prepreps for aeronautical primary structures in substitution of the thermosets.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The contribution of the European Union, which funded the project NHYTE “New Hybrid Thermoplastic Composite Aerostructures manufactured by Out of Autoclave Continuous Automated Technologies” in the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 723309, is acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. J. Kenny, A. D’Amore, L. Nicolais, M. Iannone and B. Scatteia, “Processing of Amorphous PEEK and Amorphous PEEK Based Composites”, SAMPE Journal Vol.24, No4, July/August 1989
2. M. Iannone, EU Patent No 2109532 (2 March 2011).
3. M. Iannone, F. Esposito and A. Cammarano “Thermoplastic Matrix Composites for Aeronautical Applications. The Amorphous/Semicrystalline Blend Option” – Times of Polymers TOP, Ischia (Italy) 22-26 June 2014 (2004).